

Appendix A

```
clc %clear the command window
clear all %clears all the previous variables stored in the workspace
%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%% STEP 1: INPUT THE FOLLOWING
number_of_machines=22;
number_of_components=8;
machine_component_incidence_matrix=...
[0 0 0 1 0 0 0 0;0 0 1 1 0 0 0 0;0 0 0 1 0 0 0 0;...
 0 0 1 0 0 0 0 0;0 0 0 0 1 0 0 0;0 1 0 1 1 0 0 0;...
 0 0 0 0 1 0 1 0;0 0 0 0 0 1 0 0;0 1 0 0 0 1 0 0;...
 0 1 0 0 0 1 0 0;0 0 0 0 0 1 0 0;0 1 0 0 0 1 0 1;...
 0 1 0 1 1 0 1 0;1 0 1 0 0 1 0 1;0 0 1 0 0 0 0 0;...
 1 0 1 0 0 0 0 0;0 1 0 1 0 0 0 0;0 0 0 0 0 0 1 0;...
 0 0 0 0 0 1 0 0;0 0 1 0 0 0 0 0;0 0 0 0 0 1 0 0;...
 0 0 0 0 0 1 0 0;];
size_of_population_of_machine_chromosomes=80;
size_of_population_of_component_chromosomes=80; %%%%%%%%%%% these two values should be the
same
generation_counter=1;
maximum_number_of_generations=500;
mutation_propability=10; %as a percentage
cross_over_probability=20; %as a percentage,
weighting_factor=0.5;
grouping_efficiency_matrix=zeros(size_of_population_of_component_chromosomes,1);
grouping_efficacy_matrix=zeros(size_of_population_of_component_chromosomes,1);
best_machine_chromosome_matrix=zeros(maximum_number_of_generations,number_of_machines);
best_component_chromosome_matrix=zeros(maximum_number_of_generations,number_of_compon
ents);
best_efficiency_matrix=zeros(maximum_number_of_generations,1);
generation_counter_matrix=zeros(maximum_number_of_generations,1);
main_output_matrix=zeros(maximum_number_of_generations,1+1+number_of_machines+number_o
f_components);
%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%% END OF STEP 1

%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%% STEP 2 MAXIMUM NUMBER OF CELLS
maximum_number_of_cells=min(floor(number_of_machines/2),floor(number_of_components/2));
%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%% END OF STEP 2

%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%STEP 3 INITIALIZATION
machine_chromosome_matrix=zeros(size_of_population_of_machine_chromosomes,number_of_mac
hines);
component_chromosome_matrix=zeros(size_of_population_of_component_chromosomes,number_of
_components);
first_counter=1;
while first_counter<=size_of_population_of_machine_chromosomes
```

```

machine_chromosome_matrix(first_counter,:)=randi(maximum_number_of_cells,1,number_of_machines);
    first_counter=first_counter+1;
end
machine_chromosome_matrix;
%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%% END OF STEP 3 INITIALIZATION

%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%STEP 4 IDEAL SEED
first_counter=1;
while first_counter<=size_of_population_of_machine_chromosomes
    machine_chromosome_under_process=machine_chromosome_matrix(first_counter,:);
    component_chromosome_under_process=component_chromosome_matrix(first_counter,:);
    number_of_try_counter=1;
    while number_of_try_counter<=100
        number_of_machine_groups=size(unique(machine_chromosome_under_process),2);
        machine_groups_incidence_matrix=zeros(number_of_machine_groups,number_of_components);
        second_counter_group_counter=1;
        while second_counter_group_counter<=number_of_machine_groups

            third_counter_machine_chromosome_counter=1;
            while third_counter_machine_chromosome_counter<=number_of_machines

                if
(machine_chromosome_under_process(1,third_counter_machine_chromosome_counter)==second_counter_group_counter)

                    machine_groups_incidence_matrix(second_counter_group_counter,:)=machine_groups_incidence_matrix(second_counter_group_counter,:)+machine_component_incidence_matrix(third_counter_machine_chromosome_counter,:);
                end

                third_counter_machine_chromosome_counter=third_counter_machine_chromosome_counter+1;
            end
            second_counter_group_counter=second_counter_group_counter+1;
        end
        if(~isrow(machine_groups_incidence_matrix))

            [dummy_matrix_one,component_chromosome_under_process]=max(machine_groups_incidence_matrix);
        end

        if(isrow(machine_groups_incidence_matrix))
            component_chromosome_under_process(1,:)=1;
        end
        number_of_component_groups=size(unique(component_chromosome_under_process),2);
        component_chromosome_under_process;
        number_of_machine_groups=size(unique(machine_chromosome_under_process),2);

```

```

        if (number_of_component_groups==number_of_machine_groups)
            machine_chromosome_matrix(first_counter,:)=
machine_chromosome_under_process;
component_chromosome_matrix(first_counter,:)=component_chromosome_under_process;

            break;
        end
number_of_component_groups=size(unique(component_chromosome_under_process),2);
component_groups_incidence_matrix=zeros(number_of_machines,number_of_component_groups);
second_counter_group_counter=1;
while second_counter_group_counter<=number_of_component_groups
    third_counter_component_chromosome_counter=1;
    while third_counter_component_chromosome_counter<=number_of_components
        if
(component_chromosome_under_process(1,third_counter_component_chromosome_counter)==second_counter_group_counter)
component_groups_incidence_matrix(:,second_counter_group_counter)=component_groups_incidence_matrix(:,second_counter_group_counter)+machine_component_incidence_matrix(:,third_counter_component_chromosome_counter);
        end
        third_counter_component_chromosome_counter=third_counter_component_chromosome_counter+1;
    end
    second_counter_group_counter=second_counter_group_counter+1;
end
if (~iscolumn(component_groups_incidence_matrix))

[dummy_matrix_two,machine_chromosome_under_process]=max(transpose(component_groups_incidence_matrix));
end
if (iscolumn(component_groups_incidence_matrix))
    machine_chromosome_under_process(1,:)=1;
end
machine_chromosome_under_process;
number_of_component_groups=size(unique(component_chromosome_under_process),2);
number_of_machine_groups=size(unique(machine_chromosome_under_process),2);
    if (number_of_component_groups==number_of_machine_groups)
        machine_chromosome_matrix(first_counter,:)=
machine_chromosome_under_process;

component_chromosome_matrix(first_counter,:)=component_chromosome_under_process;
        break;
    end
    number_of_try_counter=number_of_try_counter+1;
    machine_chromosome_under_process;
    component_chromosome_under_process;
end
    first_counter=first_counter+1;
end

```

```
machine_chromosome_matrix;
component_chromosome_matrix;
```

```
%%%%%%%%%%%%%% REPAIR OF CHROMOSOMES
```

```
repair_counter=1;
```

```
while repair_counter<=size_of_population_of_machine_chromosomes
```

```
%%%%%%%%%%%%%%REPAIR FOR THE MACHINE
CHROMOSOME STEP 7.3
```

```
machine_chromosome_under_process=machine_chromosome_matrix(repair_counter,:);
```

```
maximum_number_in_the_chromosome=max(machine_chromosome_under_process);
```

```
element_counter=1;
```

```
while element_counter<=maximum_number_in_the_chromosome
```

```
if (~ismember(element_counter,machine_chromosome_under_process))
```

```
repair_counter;
```

```
gene_new_value=0;
```

```
gene_position_counter=1;
```

```
while gene_position_counter<=number_of_machines
```

```
gene_old_value=machine_chromosome_under_process(1,gene_position_counter);
```

```
if (gene_old_value==gene_new_value)
```

```
gene_new_value=gene_new_value;
```

```
end
```

```
if (gene_old_value>gene_new_value)
```

```
gene_new_value=gene_new_value+1;
```

```
gene_update_counter=gene_position_counter;
```

```
while gene_update_counter<=number_of_machines
```

```
gene_current_value=machine_chromosome_under_process(1,gene_update_counter);
```

```
if (gene_current_value==gene_old_value)
```

```
machine_chromosome_under_process(1,gene_update_counter)=gene_new_value;
```

```
end
```

```
gene_update_counter=gene_update_counter+1;
```

```
end
```

```
end
```

```
gene_position_counter=gene_position_counter+1;
```

```
end
```

```
break;
```

```
end
```

```
element_counter=element_counter+1;
```

```
end
```

```
%%%%%%%%%%%%%% repair for component chromosome
```

```
component_chromosome_under_process=component_chromosome_matrix(repair_counter,:);
```

```
maximum_number_in_the_chromosome=max(component_chromosome_under_process);
```

```

element_counter=1;
while element_counter<=maximum_number_in_the_chromosome
    if (~ismember(element_counter,component_chromosome_under_process))
        gene_new_value=0;
        gene_position_counter=1;
        while gene_position_counter<=number_of_components

gene_old_value=component_chromosome_under_process(1,gene_position_counter);
        if (gene_old_value==gene_new_value)
            %gene_new_value=gene_new_value;

        end
        if (gene_old_value>gene_new_value)
            gene_new_value=gene_new_value+1;
            gene_update_counter=gene_position_counter;
            while gene_update_counter<=number_of_components

gene_current_value=component_chromosome_under_process(1,gene_update_counter);
                if (gene_current_value==gene_old_value)

component_chromosome_under_process(1,gene_update_counter)=gene_new_value;
                    end
                    gene_update_counter=gene_update_counter+1;
                    end
                    end
                    gene_position_counter=gene_position_counter+1;
                end
            break;
        end
        element_counter=element_counter+1;
    end

%%%%%%%%%%%%% EQUALIZE THE NUMBER OF MACHINE CELLS AND
COMPONENTS
%%%%%%%%%%%%% CELLS

number_of_machine_cells=size(unique(machine_chromosome_under_process),2);
number_of_component_cells=size(unique(component_chromosome_under_process),2);
if (number_of_machine_cells==number_of_component_cells )
    %do nothing
end
if (number_of_machine_cells~=number_of_component_cells)
    number_of_cells_difference=abs(number_of_machine_cells-number_of_component_cells);
    if (number_of_machine_cells>number_of_component_cells)
        equalizing_counter=1;
        while equalizing_counter<=number_of_cells_difference
            cell_to_be_removed=max(machine_chromosome_under_process);
            secondary_equalizing_counter=1;

```

```

        while secondary_equalizing_counter<=number_of_machines
            if
(machine_chromosome_under_process(1,secondary_equalizing_counter)==cell_to_be_removed)

machine_chromosome_under_process(1,secondary_equalizing_counter)=1;%equalizing it it the first
cell or group.

                end
                secondary_equalizing_counter=secondary_equalizing_counter+1;
            end
            equalizing_counter=equalizing_counter+1;
        end
    end

    if (number_of_machine_cells<number_of_component_cells)
        equalizing_counter=1;
        while equalizing_counter<=number_of_cells_difference
            cell_to_be_removed=max(component_chromosome_under_process);
            secondary_equalizing_counter=1;
            while secondary_equalizing_counter<=number_of_components
                if
(component_chromosome_under_process(1,secondary_equalizing_counter)==cell_to_be_removed)

component_chromosome_under_process(1,secondary_equalizing_counter)=1;%equalizing it it the
first cell or group.

                    end
                    secondary_equalizing_counter=secondary_equalizing_counter+1;
                end
                equalizing_counter=equalizing_counter+1;
            end
        end
    end

end

machine_chromosome_matrix(repair_counter,:)=machine_chromosome_under_process;
component_chromosome_matrix(repair_counter,:)=component_chromosome_under_process;

repair_counter=repair_counter+1;
end
%%%%%%%%%%END OF REPAIR CHROMOSOMES
machine_chromosome_matrix;
component_chromosome_matrix;
first_counter=1;
while first_counter<=size_of_population_of_machine_chromosomes

machine_chromosome_under_process=machine_chromosome_matrix(first_counter,:);
component_chromosome_under_process=component_chromosome_matrix(first_counter,:);

number_of_ones_in_diagonal_blocks=0;

```

```

number_of_zeros_in_diagonal_blocks=0;
number_of_ones_in_off_diagonal_blocks=0;
number_of_zeros_in_off_diagonal_blocks=0;

machine_counter=1;
while machine_counter<=number_of_machines
group_of_the_machine=machine_chromosome_under_process(1,machine_counter);

    component_counter=1;
    while component_counter<=number_of_components
        group_of_the_component=component_chromosome_under_process(1,component_counter);
        if (group_of_the_machine==group_of_the_component)
            if (machine_component_incidence_matrix(machine_counter,component_counter)==1)
                number_of_ones_in_diagonal_blocks=number_of_ones_in_diagonal_blocks+1;
            end
            if (machine_component_incidence_matrix(machine_counter,component_counter)==0)

number_of_zeros_in_diagonal_blocks=number_of_zeros_in_diagonal_blocks+1;
                end
                end
                if (group_of_the_machine ~= group_of_the_component) %% we are in an off-diagonal
area
                    if (machine_component_incidence_matrix(machine_counter,component_counter)==1)

number_of_ones_in_off_diagonal_blocks=number_of_ones_in_off_diagonal_blocks+1;
                        end
                        if (machine_component_incidence_matrix(machine_counter,component_counter)==0)

number_of_zeros_in_off_diagonal_blocks=number_of_zeros_in_off_diagonal_blocks+1;
                            end
                            end

                    component_counter=component_counter+1;
                end

            machine_counter=machine_counter+1;
        end

        total_number_of_elements_in_diagonal_blocks=number_of_ones_in_diagonal_blocks+number_of_zeros_in_diagonal_blocks;
        total_number_of_elements_in_off_diagonal_blocks=number_of_ones_in_off_diagonal_blocks+number_of_zeros_in_off_diagonal_blocks;
        grouping_efficiency_matrix(first_counter,1)=...

        (weighting_factor*(number_of_ones_in_diagonal_blocks/total_number_of_elements_in_diagonal_blocks))+...

```

```
((1-  
weighting_factor)*(number_of_zeros_in_off_diagonal_blocks/total_number_of_elements_in_off_dia  
gonal_blocks));
```

```
total_number_of_ones_in_the_matrix=number_of_ones_in_off_diagonal_blocks+number_of_ones_in  
_diagonal_blocks;
```

```
number_of_exceptional_elements=number_of_ones_in_off_diagonal_blocks;  
number_of_voids_in_the_diagonal_matrix=number_of_zeros_in_diagonal_blocks;  
%% %% %% end of grouping efficiency
```

```
first_counter=first_counter+1;
```

```
end
```

```
grouping_efficiency_matrix;
```

```
%% %% %% %% %% %% %% %% %% %% %% %% %% %% %% %% %% %% %% %% %% %% %% END OF STEP 4 IDEAL SEED
```

```
%% %% %% %% %% %% %% %% %% %% %% %% %% %% %% %% %% %% %% %% %% %% %% STEP 5 SORT THE POPULATION
```

```
sorted_number_of_population=round(size_of_population_of_machine_chromosomes*0.3);
```

```
if (rem(sorted_number_of_population,2)~=0)
```

```
sorted_number_of_population=sorted_number_of_population+1;
```

```
end
```

```
sorted_machine_chromosome_matrix=zeros(sorted_number_of_population,number_of_machines);
```

```
sorted_component_chromosome_matrix=zeros(sorted_number_of_population,number_of_component  
s);
```

```
[sorted_efficiency_matrix,sorted_index_matrix]=sort(grouping_efficiency_matrix);
```

```
sorted_efficiency_matrix;
```

```
sorted_index_matrix;
```

```
%% %% %% %% %% %% %% %% %% %% %% %% %% %% %% %% %% %% %% %% %% %% %% END OF STEP 5 SORT THE POPULATION
```

```
%% %% %% %% %% %% %% %% %% %% %% %% %% %% %% %% %% %% %% %% %% %% %% STEP 6 SELECT THE TOP 30
```

```
sorted_population_counter=1;
```

```
sort_first_counter=size_of_population_of_machine_chromosomes;
```

```
while sort_first_counter>=1
```

```
sorted_efficiency_value=sorted_efficiency_matrix(sort_first_counter,1);
```

```
if (~isnan(sorted_efficiency_value))
```

```
index_of_the_sorted_value=sorted_index_matrix(sort_first_counter,1);
```

```
sorted_machine_chromosome_matrix(sorted_population_counter,:)=machine_chromosome_matrix(in  
dex_of_the_sorted_value,:);
```

```
sorted_component_chromosome_matrix(sorted_population_counter,:)=component_chromosome_mat  
rix(index_of_the_sorted_value,:);
```

```
if (sorted_population_counter>=sorted_number_of_population)
```

```
break;
```

```
end
```

```
sorted_population_counter=sorted_population_counter+1;
```

```
end
```

```
sort_first_counter=sort_first_counter-1;
end
```

```
sorted_machine_chromosome_matrix
sorted_component_chromosome_matrix
size(sorted_component_chromosome_matrix);
size(sorted_machine_chromosome_matrix);
%%%%%%%%%%END OF STEP 6 SELECT THE
TOP 30
```

```
generation_counter=1;
while generation_counter<=maximum_number_of_generations
```

```
%%%%%%%%%% STEP 7.1 TWO-POINT
CROSSOVER
```

```
first_machine_chromosome_for_crossover=zeros(1,number_of_machines);
second_mchine_chromosme_for_crossover=zeros(1,number_of_machines);
first_component_chromosome_for_crossover=zeros(1,number_of_components);
second_component_chromosome_for_crossover=zeros(1,number_of_components);
location_of_the_crossover_for_the_machine_chromosome=randi(number_of_machines,1,2);
location_of_the_crossover_for_the_component_chromosome=randi(number_of_components,1,2);
first_value_for_crossover=0;
second_value_for_crossover=0;
```

```
crossover_counter=1;
while (crossover_counter<=sorted_number_of_population)
    if (randi(100)<=cross_over_probability
```

```
first_machine_chromosome_for_crossover(1,:)=sorted_machine_chromosome_matrix(crossover_cou
nter,:);
```

```
second_machine_chromosome_for_crossover(1,:)=sorted_machine_chromosome_matrix(crossover_c
ounter+1,:);
```

```
first_value_for_crossover=first_machine_chromosome_for_crossover(1,location_of_the_crossover_fo
r_the_machine_chromosome(1,1));
```

```
second_value_for_crossover=second_machine_chromosome_for_crossover(1,location_of_the_crosso
ver_for_the_machine_chromosome(1,2));
```

```
first_machine_chromosome_for_crossover(1,location_of_the_crossover_for_the_machine_chromoso
me(1,1))=second_value_for_crossover;
```

```
second_machine_chromosome_for_crossover(1,location_of_the_crossover_for_the_machine_chromo
some(1,2))=first_value_for_crossover;
```

```
first_value_for_crossover=first_machine_chromosome_for_crossover(1,location_of_the_crossover_fo
```

```

r_the_machine_chromosome(1,2));
second_value_for_crossover=second_machine_chromosome_for_crossover(1,location_of_the_crossover_for_the_machine_chromosome(1,1));
first_machine_chromosome_for_crossover(1,location_of_the_crossover_for_the_machine_chromosome(1,2))=second_value_for_crossover;
second_machine_chromosome_for_crossover(1,location_of_the_crossover_for_the_machine_chromosome(1,1))=first_value_for_crossover;
sorted_machine_chromosome_matrix(crossover_counter,:)=first_machine_chromosome_for_crossover(1,:);
sorted_machine_chromosome_matrix(crossover_counter+1,:)=second_machine_chromosome_for_crossover(1,:);
first_component_chromosome_for_crossover(1,:)=sorted_component_chromosome_matrix(crossover_counter,:);
second_component_chromosome_for_crossover(1,:)=sorted_component_chromosome_matrix(crossover_counter+1,:);
first_value_for_crossover=first_component_chromosome_for_crossover(1,location_of_the_crossover_for_the_component_chromosome(1,1));
second_value_for_crossover=second_component_chromosome_for_crossover(1,location_of_the_crossover_for_the_component_chromosome(1,2));
first_component_chromosome_for_crossover(1,location_of_the_crossover_for_the_component_chromosome(1,1))=second_value_for_crossover;
second_component_chromosome_for_crossover(1,location_of_the_crossover_for_the_component_chromosome(1,2))=first_value_for_crossover;
first_value_for_crossover=first_component_chromosome_for_crossover(1,location_of_the_crossover_for_the_component_chromosome(1,2));
second_value_for_crossover=second_component_chromosome_for_crossover(1,location_of_the_crossover_for_the_component_chromosome(1,1));
first_component_chromosome_for_crossover(1,location_of_the_crossover_for_the_component_chromosome(1,2))=second_value_for_crossover;
second_component_chromosome_for_crossover(1,location_of_the_crossover_for_the_component_chromosome(1,1))=first_value_for_crossover;
sorted_component_chromosome_matrix(crossover_counter,:)=first_component_chromosome_for_crossover(1,:);
sorted_component_chromosome_matrix(crossover_counter+1,:)=second_component_chromosome_for_crossover(1,:);
    end
crossover_counter=crossover_counter+2;
end
%%%%%%%%%% END OF STEP TWO-POINT
CROSS OVER

sorted_machine_chromosome_matrix;

%%%%%%%%%%STEP 7.2 MUTATION
mutation_counter=1;
while mutation_counter<=sorted_number_of_population

    if (randi(100)<=mutation_propapility)

```

```

sorted_machine_chromosome_matrix(mutation_counter,randi(number_of_machines))=randi(maximu
m_number_of_cells);
sorted_component_chromosome_matrix(mutation_counter,randi(number_of_components))=randi(ma
ximum_number_of_cells);
    end
mutation_counter=mutation_counter+1;
end
%%%%%%%%%% END OF STEP MUTATION
sorted_machine_chromosome_matrix;

%%%%%%%%%% STEP REPAIR OF CHROMOSOMES /
repair_counter=1;
while repair_counter<=sorted_number_of_population

%%%%%%%%%% REPAIR FOR THE MACHINE
CHROMOSOME
machine_chromosome_under_process=sorted_machine_chromosome_matrix(repair_counter,:);
maximum_number_in_the_chromosome=max(machine_chromosome_under_process);

    element_counter=1;
    while element_counter<=maximum_number_in_the_chromosome
        if (~ismember(element_counter,machine_chromosome_under_process))
            repair_counter;
                gene_new_value=0;
                gene_position_counter=1;
                while gene_position_counter<=number_of_machines

gene_old_value=machine_chromosome_under_process(1,gene_position_counter);
                    if (gene_old_value==gene_new_value)
                        %gene_new_value=gene_new_value;

                    end
                    if (gene_old_value>gene_new_value)
                        gene_new_value=gene_new_value+1;
                        gene_update_counter=gene_position_counter;
                        while gene_update_counter<=number_of_machines

gene_current_value=machine_chromosome_under_process(1,gene_update_counter);
                            if (gene_current_value==gene_old_value)

machine_chromosome_under_process(1,gene_update_counter)=gene_new_value;
                                end
                                    gene_update_counter=gene_update_counter+1;
                                end
                                    end
                                    end

```

```

        gene_position_counter=gene_position_counter+1;
    end
    break;
end
    element_counter=element_counter+1;
end
%%%%%% repair for component chromosome
component_chromosome_under_process=sorted_component_chromosome_matrix(repair_counter,:);
maximum_number_in_the_chromosome=max(component_chromosome_under_process);

element_counter=1;
while element_counter<=maximum_number_in_the_chromosome
    if (~ismember(element_counter,component_chromosome_under_process))
        gene_new_value=0;
        gene_position_counter=1;
        while gene_position_counter<=number_of_components

gene_old_value=component_chromosome_under_process(1,gene_position_counter);
        if (gene_old_value==gene_new_value)
            %gene_new_value=gene_new_value;

        end
        if (gene_old_value>gene_new_value)
            gene_new_value=gene_new_value+1;
            gene_update_counter=gene_position_counter;
            while gene_update_counter<=number_of_components

gene_current_value=component_chromosome_under_process(1,gene_update_counter);
                if (gene_current_value==gene_old_value)

component_chromosome_under_process(1,gene_update_counter)=gene_new_value;
                    end
                    gene_update_counter=gene_update_counter+1;
                end
            end
        gene_position_counter=gene_position_counter+1;
        end
        break;
    end
    element_counter=element_counter+1;
end

%%%%%%%% EQUALIZE THE NUMBER OF MACHINE CELLS AND
COMPONENTS
%%%%%%%% CELLS

number_of_machine_cells=size(unique(machine_chromosome_under_process),2);

```

```

number_of_component_cells=size(unique(component_chromosome_under_process),2);
if (number_of_machine_cells==number_of_component_cells )

end
if (number_of_machine_cells~=number_of_component_cells)
    number_of_cells_difference=abs(number_of_machine_cells-number_of_component_cells);
    if (number_of_machine_cells>number_of_component_cells)
        equalizing_counter=1;
        while equalizing_counter<=number_of_cells_difference
            cell_to_be_removed=max(machine_chromosome_under_process);
            secondary_equalizing_counter=1;
            while secondary_equalizing_counter<=number_of_machines
                if
(machine_chromosome_under_process(1,secondary_equalizing_counter)==cell_to_be_removed)

machine_chromosome_under_process(1,secondary_equalizing_counter)=1;%equalizing it it the first
cell or group.

                    end
                    secondary_equalizing_counter=secondary_equalizing_counter+1;
                end
            end
            equalizing_counter=equalizing_counter+1;
        end
    end

    if (number_of_machine_cells<number_of_component_cells)
        equalizing_counter=1;
        while equalizing_counter<=number_of_cells_difference
            cell_to_be_removed=max(component_chromosome_under_process);
            secondary_equalizing_counter=1;
            while secondary_equalizing_counter<=number_of_components
                if
(component_chromosome_under_process(1,secondary_equalizing_counter)==cell_to_be_removed)

component_chromosome_under_process(1,secondary_equalizing_counter)=1;%equalizing it it the
first cell or group.

                    end
                    secondary_equalizing_counter=secondary_equalizing_counter+1;
                end
            end
            equalizing_counter=equalizing_counter+1;
        end
    end
end

sorted_machine_chromosome_matrix(repair_counter,:)=machine_chromosome_under_process;
sorted_component_chromosome_matrix(repair_counter,:)=component_chromosome_under_process;
repair_counter=repair_counter+1;
end

```

```
%%%%%%%%%% END OF STEP REPAIR CHROMOSOMES
sorted_machine_chromosome_matrix;
```

```
%%%%%%%%%% STEP DENSITY MATRIX
```

```
grouping_efficiency_matrix=zeros(sorted_number_of_population,1);
grouping_efficacy_matrix=zeros(sorted_number_of_population,1);
density_first_counter=1;
while density_first_counter<=sorted_number_of_population
machine_chromosome_under_process=sorted_machine_chromosome_matrix(density_first_counter,:);
```

```
component_chromosome_under_process=sorted_component_chromosome_matrix(density_first_counter,:);
```

```
%%%%%%%%%% forming of the density matrix
```

```
density_number_of_zeros=0;
density_number_of_ones=0;
number_of_groups=max(machine_chromosome_under_process); %or
max(component_under_process);
density_matrix=zeros(number_of_groups,number_of_groups);
density_component_group_counter=1;
while density_component_group_counter<=number_of_groups
density_machine_group_counter=1;
while density_machine_group_counter<=number_of_groups
density_component_counter=1;
while density_component_counter<=number_of_components
if
(component_chromosome_under_process(1,density_component_counter)==density_component_group_counter)
density_machine_counter=1;
while density_machine_counter<=number_of_machines
if
(machine_chromosome_under_process(1,density_machine_counter)==density_machine_group_counter)
if
(machine_component_incidence_matrix(density_machine_counter,density_component_counter)==1)
density_number_of_ones=density_number_of_ones+1;
end
if
(machine_component_incidence_matrix(density_machine_counter,density_component_counter)==0)
density_number_of_zeros=density_number_of_zeros+1;
end
end
density_machine_counter=density_machine_counter+1;
end
end
density_component_counter=density_component_counter+1;
end
```

```

density_matrix(density_machine_group_counter,density_component_group_counter)=((density_number_of_ones)/(density_number_of_ones+density_number_of_zeros));
    density_machine_group_counter=density_machine_group_counter+1;
end
    density_component_group_counter=density_component_group_counter+1;
end
    number_of_groups=max(machine_chromosome_under_process); %or
max(component_under_process);
    density_permutation_matrix=perms(1:number_of_groups);
    [number_of_permutations,dummy_variable]=size(density_permutation_matrix);
    density_permutation_summation_matrix=zeros(number_of_permutations,1);
    permutation_counter=1;
    while permutation_counter<=number_of_permutations
        density_summation=0;
        permutation_group_counter=1;
        while permutation_group_counter<=number_of_groups
            density_value=density_matrix(density_permutation_matrix(permutation_counter,permutation_group_counter),permutation_group_counter);
            density_summation=density_summation+density_value;
            permutation_group_counter=permutation_group_counter+1;
        end
        density_permutation_summation_matrix(permutation_counter,1)=density_summation;
        permutation_counter=permutation_counter+1;
    end

[dummy_density_variable,location_of_the_best_permutation]=max(density_permutation_summation_matrix);
    best_permutation=density_permutation_matrix(location_of_the_best_permutation,:);
    density_component_chromosome=zeros(2,number_of_components);
    density_component_chromosome(1,:)=component_chromosome_under_process;
    density_component_chromosome_counter=1;
    while density_component_chromosome_counter<=number_of_components

density_component_old_group=density_component_chromosome(1,density_component_chromosome_counter);
        density_component_new_group=best_permutation(1,density_component_old_group);

density_component_chromosome(2,density_component_chromosome_counter)=density_component_new_group;
        density_component_chromosome_counter=density_component_chromosome_counter+1;
    end
    component_chromosome_under_process=density_component_chromosome(2,:);
% THIS IS THE RE-ASSIGNING OF THE FAMILIES OR GROUPS, THE MACHINE
CHROMOSOME REMAINS THE SAME, BUT THE COMPONENT CHROMOSOME CHANGES.

```

STEP STORING THE OFFSPRING

```
sorted_machine_chromosome_matrix(density_first_counter,:)=machine_chromosome_under_process;
sorted_component_chromosome_matrix(density_first_counter,:)=component_chromosome_under_pr
ocess;
```

```
density_first_counter=density_first_counter+1;
end
```

```
%%%%%%%%%% END OF STEP DENSITY MATRIX
```

```
x='before sorting';
```

```
sorted_machine_chromosome_matrix;
```

```
grouping_efficiency_matrix;
```

```
%%%%%%%%%% STEP SORTING OF THE
CHROMOSOMES
```

```
[sorted_efficiency_matrix,sorted_index_matrix]=sort(grouping_efficiency_matrix);
```

```
sorted_efficiency_matrix;
```

```
new_sorted_machine_chromosome_matrix=zeros(sorted_number_of_population,number_of_machine
s);
```

```
new_sorted_component_chromosome_matrix=zeros(sorted_number_of_population,number_of_comp
onents);
```

```
sorted_population_counter=1;
```

```
sort_first_counter=sorted_number_of_population;
```

```
while sort_first_counter>=1
```

```
sorted_efficiency_value=sorted_efficiency_matrix(sort_first_counter,1);
```

```
if (~isnan(sorted_efficiency_value))
```

```
index_of_the_sorted_value=sorted_index_matrix(sort_first_counter,1);
```

```
new_sorted_machine_chromosome_matrix(sorted_population_counter,:)=sorted_machine_chromo
me_matrix(index_of_the_sorted_value,:);
```

```
new_sorted_component_chromosome_matrix(sorted_population_counter,:)=sorted_component_chro
mosome_matrix(index_of_the_sorted_value,:);
```

```
if (sorted_population_counter>=sorted_number_of_population)
```

```
break;
```

```
end
```

```
sorted_population_counter=sorted_population_counter+1;
```

```
end
```

```
sort_first_counter=sort_first_counter-1;
```

```
end
```

```
sorted_machine_chromosome_matrix=new_sorted_machine_chromosome_matrix;
```

```
sorted_component_chromosome_matrix=new_sorted_component_chromosome_matrix;
```

```
%%%%%%%%%% END OF STEP SORTING OF THE
CHROMOSOMES
```

```
best_chromosome_efficiency=max(grouping_efficiency_matrix); %%%%%%%%%%%
FIRST OUTPUT
```

```
best_chromosome_matrix(generation_counter,1)=generation_counter;
```

```
best_chromosome_matrix(generation_counter,2)=best_chromosome_efficiency;
```

```
best_machine_chromosome_matrix(generation_counter,:)=sorted_machine_chromosome_matrix(1,:);
```

```

best_component_chromosome_matrix(generation_counter,:)=sorted_component_chromosome_matrix
(1,:);
best_efficiency_matrix(generation_counter,1)=max(grouping_efficiency_matrix);
generation_counter_matrix(generation_counter,1)=generation_counter;

x='after sorting';

sorted_machine_chromosome_matrix;
sorted_component_chromosome_matrix;
generation_counter;

generation_counter=generation_counter+1;
end
main_output_matrix=[generation_counter_matrix best_efficiency_matrix
best_machine_chromosome_matrix best_component_chromosome_matrix];

main_output_matrix=sortrows(main_output_matrix,2,'descend')
current_time=datestr(now, 'dd_mm_yy_HH_MM_SS');
excel_directory=char(strcat('E:\chapter 5\Experimental chapter 4\',current_time, '.xlsx')); % CHANGE
THIS PATH ACCORDING TO YOUR COMPUTER
filename=excel_directory
xlswrite(filename,main_output_matrix)
plot(best_chromosome_matrix(:,1),best_chromosome_matrix(:,2),'lineWidth',1,'color','red');
title('best efficiency in the generation PLOT');
xlabel('Generation');
ylabel('Best Efficiency in this Generation');
grid("on");
grid minor;

```